

FRAZEOLOGIK BIRLIKLARNING GRAMATIK TARKIBI

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Annotasiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi zoonim kanseptli frazeologik birliklar haqida ma'lumotlar yoritildi. Shuningdek maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi zoonim kanseptli frazeologik birliklar misollar orqali ko'rsatib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Frazeologiya, frazeologik birliklar, zoonimlar, zoonim birliklar.

GRAMMATICAL COMPOSITION OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

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Abstract: This article provides information about phraseological units with zoonym concept in English and Uzbek languages. Also, the article shows phraseological units with zoonym concept in English and Uzbek languages through examples.

Key words: Phraseology, phraseological units, zoonyms, zoonym units.

Frazeologiya – tilshunoslikning kichik sohasi bo'lib, fraza – ibora, logos – ta'limot degan ma'nolarni anglatadi. Frazeologiya atamasi asosan ikki ma'noda ishlatiladi:

- 1) tilning frazeologik tarkibini o'rganuvchi tilshunoslik sohasi;
- 2) shu tilning frazeologizmi majmui.

Frazeologiyaning o'rganish predmeti frazeologizmning tabiati va substansional xususiyatlari hamda ularning nutqda amal qilish qonuniyatidir. Ikki va undan ortiq so'zdan tarkib topgan, yaxlit bir ko'chma ma'no ifodalaydigan, ta'sirchanlikka ega bo'lgan va ma'nosi bir so'zga teng ma'nodagi so'zlar yig'indisi yoki gaplar yig'indisi ibora deyiladi. Iboralar tilshunoslikning frazeologiya bo'limida o'rganiladi, shuning uchun ham iboralarni frazeologizmlar deb ham ataymiz. Bundan tashqari tilshunoslikning frazeologiya bo'limi shu sohaning taraqqiyoti, frazeologiya sohasiga muhim hissa qo'shgan tilshunos olimlar, frazeologik ma'no, frazeologik polisemiya, qarama qarshi ma'noli iboralar, iboralar sinonimiyasi, frazeologik paronimiya va paraforma, iboralar omonimiyasi, iboralar variatsiyasi, frazeologizmlarning o'ziga xos grammatik xususiyatlari va boshqalar o'rganiladi.

Ma'lumki, tilshunoslikda frazeologiya uzoq yillar davomida leksikologiya tarkibida o'rganib kelingan. Chunki frazeologik birliklar tildagi so'zlarning ekvivalentlari

hisoblanib, leksikologiya esa tilning lug'at sostavini tashkil qiluvchi so'zlar va ularning ekvivalentlarini o'rganuvchi disiplina deb ataladi. Keyingi yillarda frazeologiya tilning alohida disipline yoki mustaqil til bosqichi bo'lganligi bois, frazeologiya - tilshunoslikning mustaqil sohasi sifatida, leksikologiya bag'ridan XX-asrning 50-yillridan boshlab mustaqil bo'lim, yangi soha sifatida ajralib chiqdi.

Frazeologik birlashmalar ma'lum darajada semantik jihatdan bo'linmasdir. Shuningdek, A.N.Smirnistkiy, Z.N.Anisimova, A.V.Kumachova, T.N.Derbulova, N.N.Amosova, N.M.Shanskiy kabi qator olimlar tomonidan ilgari surilgan frazeologizmlar klassifikatsiyalari ham mavjud. Bular haqida ishning ma'lum bob va bo'linmalarida to'xtalamiz. Frazeologik birliklar ifoda plani bilan mazmun planning o'ziga xos qarama-qarshiligi va birligi asosida yuzaga keluvchi murakkab hodisa bo'lgani uchun alohida yondashish va o'rganishini talab etadi

FBlar tarkibiga har qanday so'z turkumi kirishi mumkin. FBlar bilan kontekst o'rtasidagi munosabatda FBlarining grammatik qurilishi muhim rol o'ynaydi. FBlar leksik birliklarva qo'shma so'zlar qatorida so'z turkumlari kabi leksik-grammatik jihatdan tahlil qilinadi.

Masalan, O'tli (substantiv) FBlar predmetni bildiradi;

Fe'lli (verbial) FBlar ish-harakatni bildiradi;

Sifatli (ad'ektiv) FBlar biror narsaning xususiyatini, sifatini anglatadi;

Ravishli (adverbial) FBlar holat, daraja va x.k.ni bildiradi.

Turg'un so'z birliklari sintaktik birliklarga bo'linmaydilar va har doim gapda yaxlit holda ma'lum bir gap bo'lagi vazifasida keladilar. Quyida biz ZKFBlarni so'z turkumlariga nisbatan 5 turga ajratdik:

1. O'tli ZKFBlar
2. Fe'lli ZKFBlar
3. Sifatli ZKFBlar
4. Ravishli ZKFBlar
5. Undovli ZKFBlar

I. O'tli ZKFBlarda butun bir birikmaning o'zi kim?, nima? so'rog'iga javob bo'ladi. To'plangan zoonimik komponentli frazeologik birliklar ichida 42%, ya'ni 420tasi o'tli ZKFBlardir. O'tli frazeologik birikmalar asosan Adj+N - konstruksiyasi shaklida tuzilgan bo'lib, quyidagi ma'nolarni bildiradi:

1. A dead dog – keraksiz inson, foydasiz inson. You're no more use than a dead dog. We'll just have to go along the reef till we find the opening. [Maugham]
2. Top dog – boshliq: "Do you suppose yourself top dog in this house?", "Yes, Soames:", "Oh, then you can go back to France tomorrow".[Galsworthy]
3. A sly dog– ayyor kishi: You're a sly dog. Hand in glove with the great detective, and not a hint to the way things are going.

4. Yellow dog – qo‘rqoq kishi Believing they were attacked by Indians, the settlers ran from their beds and were there seized by Andy's men as fast as they appeared. "Search the houses "- he said. Bring all the yellow dogs out. [Fisher]
5. A fair cow – yolg‘onchi, firibgar. I had a fair cow of a horse called Grasshopper. [Prichard]
6. A white crow – tasodifiy hodisa. A black swan Shirley had the air of a black swan or white crow in the midst, of this party. [Bronte]
7. The dogs of war – urush dahshatlari. Disease, famine and death are the dogs of war.
8. A dumb dog – hotirjam kishi Proteus : "If his Majesty wants a Cabinet of dumb dogs he will not get it from my party ".
9. Hot dog: a) issiq sosiska bilan bulochka. On their evening off they went economically to an imitation Coney Island...and with great pleasure they ate hot dogs pain stakingly they rode the scenic railway. [Lewis] b) hot dog – mashhur sportchi: Alston Mackintosh...was a real hot dog. c) hot dog – ajoyib ish! The Major could see every unit in the Army using his idea at last: Hot dog! Tarkibida «it” zoonimi bo‘lgan FBlar o‘zbek tilida ham juda ko‘p. Ular ikki komponentli holatdan toki bir gapga teng keluvchi ko‘p komponentli iboralargacha borib yetadi: it fe‘l; it urug‘; it tinsa ham, u tinmaydi; it ham dumi bilan atrofini tozalab o‘tiradi kabilar.
9. A white elephant – ko‘p xarajat talab qiladigan narsa: Wickford Point isn't a farm – it's a white elephant. It catches up money faster than I can make it. [Maugham]
10. A cold fish – hissiz kishi: "Then you locked the door and searched him at once". Yes, you'll think Iam a cold fish. Well, may be I am.
11. A poor fish –kambag‘al odam: If the poor fish would have his teeth x-rayed, I'll bet nine a half cents he'd find an abscess there [Lewis]
12. A willing horse – mehnatsevar kishi: If he is as good at his research work as some of us are inclined to think he should not be encumbered with more pedestrian activities. We can always find willing horses among ourselves to carry out the more pedestrian activities.
13. A black sheep –oiladagi qora dog‘: I am the black sheep of the family. I don't belong. I've violated the rules.
14. Soup and fish – smoking – tungi erkaklar kostyumi: Go home and doll up in your soup and fish, poul and wipe that worried look off your map. Tonight we gamble.
15. A black swan – ayrim hodisa: I speak of the generality, not of the few black swans among us. [Galsworthy]
16. Cold turkey – qurbon bo‘lgan narsa, yutuqqa ega bo‘lmagan narsa: “Sam” I said, “I don't know where to find anybody who would put money into a play that's already a cold turkey”.
17. Cold turkey – sovuq, hissiz kishi: He was... what we call a grouch face, a drizzle-puss, a wet blanket, a cold turkey.

18. Cold turkey – narkomanning narkotiklarni to‘xtatishi. (meditsina aralashuvisiz) Joe did a cold turkey.

19. An old bird – tajribali kishi, qariya: She rather amusses me. What a detective the old bird is!... How she enjoyed hacking down the unfortunate Carrington... [Aldington] Birinchi komponenti fe‘l bilan ifodalangan ZKFBlar lug‘atlarda juda ko‘p.

Ular hayvonlarning harakatini inson va voqealarga o‘xshatish yoki metafora usuli bilan ko‘chirishda qo‘l keladi. Masalan: to make an ass of oneself – eshakdek ahmoqona yo‘l tutmoq; to make a beast of oneself – haddan ortiq ovqat yemoq; to have a bee in one’s bonnet – bir ish bilan doimo shug‘ullanmoq; to kill two birds with one stone – bir o‘q bilan ikki qushni otmoq; to let the cat out of the bag – sirni oshkora qilmoq; to do the donkey work – og‘ir ishni bajarmoq

Xalq og‘zaki ijodi namunalarida qo‘llanilgan til strukturalari, shu jumladan, FBlarda kishilar o‘rtasidagi jamiyatdagi munosabatlar, o‘zaro ziddiyatlar, ijobiy yoki salbiy holatlarni nutqda aks ettirish, fikrlarni soddaroq, oydinroq, ta’sirchan qilib ifodalash maqsadida hayvonlarni bildiruvchi leksik qatlamdan foydalaniladi. Zoonimik leksikani “uy hayvonlari”, “yovvoyi hayvonlar”, “qushlar”, “parrandalar”, “sudralib yuruvchilar” kabi guruhlariga ajratiladi. Shuni ta’kidlash joizki, zoonimlar qaysi tilda o‘rganilgan bo‘lmasin, alohida bir yangilikni, qiziqarli, muhim xulosalarni keltirib chiqaradi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

1 Kunin A.S.Course phraseologism of the modern English language.-Moscow: Higher School,1996.-156p.

2 Bafoyeva M.Badiy nutqda frazeologik sinonimlardan foydalanish.-T.: O‘TA.2003.N;2.185 b

3 Vinogradov V.V.Leksikologiya.-M.1977.265 b

4 Yo‘ldoshev B.O‘zbek frazeologiyasi va frazeografiyasining shakllanishishi hamda taraqqiyoti.-Samarqand.2007.220 b

5 Mamatov A.O‘zbek tili frazeologizmlarining shakllanishi.-T.1997.177 b

6 Mamatov A.O‘zbek tilida frazeologizmlarning shakllanish masalalari.-T.;O‘TA.2001.230 b

7 Raxmatullayev SH.O‘zbek tili frazeologiyasining ba’zi masalalari.-T.;Akadem nashr.1985.245 b

